

The World English(es) and linguistic diversity in the English language class: proposal of a didactic activity /
O(s) World English(es) e a diversidade linguística na aula de língua inglesa: proposta de atividade didática

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ABSTRACT

Due to the process of colonization of the British Empire and the current economic and cultural impact of the United States, it is not difficult to find discourses that associate the English language exclusively with these people. However, with globalization and technological advances, authors such as Crystal (2003) argue that the English language is currently a global language, since it has a prominent role around the world, including in the educational environment. Nonetheless, such a reach of the English language does not make it, in fact, conceived as a language of all, which may even influence the learning of English as an additional language. In such manner, we find the World English(es) (BOLTON, 2006; RAJAGOPALAN, 2005), perspective that promotes a plural conception of the English language, providing a vision of this language according to a perspective of multiplicity. Thus, the aim of this article is to discuss how the World English(es) can be a tool in the dissemination of linguistic diversity in the English class. In addition, a didactic activity of English teaching will be presented, formulated through the content-based approach (LEFFA, 2016), based on the prism of the World English(es) and linguistic plurality.

KEYWORDS: World English(es); Linguistic diversity; English language teaching; Didactic activity.

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RESUMO

Devido ao processo de colonização do Império Britânico e do atual impacto econômico e cultural dos Estados Unidos, não é difícil encontrar discursos que associam a língua inglesa exclusivamente com estes povos. Entretanto, com a globalização e os avanços tecnológicos, autores como Crystal (2003) defendem que a língua inglesa é, atualmente, uma língua global, uma vez que ela possui um papel de destaque ao redor do mundo, inclusive no meio educacional. Todavia, tal alcance da língua inglesa não faz com que ela seja, de fato, concebida como uma língua de todos, o que pode, inclusive, influenciar a aprendizagem do inglês como língua adicional. Dessa maneira, encontramos o(s) World English(es) (BOLTON, 2006; RAJAGOPALAN, 2005), perspectiva que promove uma concepção plural da língua inglesa, propiciando uma visão desta língua segundo uma ótica da multiplicidade. Sendo assim, o objetivo deste artigo é discutir como o(s) World English(es) podem ser uma ferramenta na difusão da diversidade linguística na aula de língua inglesa. Além disso, será apresentada uma atividade didática de ensino de inglês, confeccionada através da abordagem baseada no conteúdo (LEFFA, 2016), pautada sob o prisma do(s) World English(es) e da pluralidade linguística.

PALAVRAS-CHAVE: *World English(es); Diversidade linguística; Ensino de língua inglesa; Atividade didática.*

1 Introduction

When it comes to the English language teaching and learning process it is not unusual to hear the question "Which English do you speak? American¹ or British?" or even find in the corner of the textbook information about the patterns followed by the material, with a signpost indicating which type of English can be found. However, from this situation, we can inquire: when a learner speaks English, do they do it solely based on an American or British variant? When a textbook claims to be based on American or British English, which English is this? Is there only one British variant and one American variant?

These situations are related to the linguistic imperialism, a phenomenon that elevates the language of certain regions to a language of prestige, while placing other variants as less relevant or non-standard. And this linguistic valuation exerts great influence in the classroom. The diffusion of certain cultures to the detriment of others leads to a cultural legitimization of American or British English, devaluing linguistic variants that the student learns outside the classroom. This may lead the student to feel as part of an inferior culture, transforming the English language class into the place of learning a language far from their reality, belonging to specific groups.

However, due to the globalization process and technological advances, the English language can be seen today as a global language (CRYSTAL, 2003). Whether through its political

¹ We have chosen the term "American English" instead of "Unitedstatian English" as the first option is the most used by English language learners. Nonetheless, we understand that "Unitedstatian" is more appropriate to refer to people or objects from the United States.

reach or its privileged use around the world, as in the educational system, English is present in the daily lives of most Brazilians. In formal ways, as in the teaching of the language in regular schools, or informal, as in games and on the Internet, Brazilian citizens come into contact with the English language, and frequently use the language even though not always do they realize it.

In an attempt to show that the English language used in the 21st century is very different from the one imposed by the violence of colonization, Rajagopalan (2005) alerts us to a possible dissociation between English and Anglo-Saxon culture. That is, the English language spoken nowadays does not have a primordial link with neither the United Kingdom nor with the United States. Besides, authors like Bolton (2006) alert us about the plurality of the English language. In other words, the English language is used by different peoples around the world and there is a unique articulation between local cultures and the English language in each of these cases. Nonetheless, such statements do not support the view that the power relations between countries and even between speakers, such as native and non-native speakers, have come to an end. So, what would be the role of teaching materials in the diffusion of a vision of the English language focused on linguistic plurality?

The aim of this article is to emphasize the concept of World English(es), showing how this view of the English language can be beneficial to its teaching if it is based on linguistic diversity. Moreover, at the end of this study, a didactic activity of English language teaching under these perspectives will be presented.

2 The World English(es)

In the age of globalization, it is a fallacy to say that English is not part of the routine of most of the inhabitants of the 21st century. Whether through films, series, songs, TV advertisements or even through the incorporation of English words in the vocabulary of the most diverse languages spread around the world, English is present. But what makes English a global language?

It is not uncommon to find as an answer to the question above the argument that the English language is easy to learn. In fact, some features of the English language can make it more attractive, such as, for example, its gender neutrality. Another argument concerns the large number of English speakers. There are about 1,132,366,680 English speakers (WORD TIPS apud IPOL,

2020). Still, we can build a parallel with Mandarin, spoken by approximately 1,116,596,640 people (WORD TIPS apud IPOL, 2020)². In this case, is it possible to state that Mandarin also has a global reach? According to Crystal (2003), intrinsic aspects of the English language, as well as the amount of people considered native speakers, do not justify its global reach. Thus, what makes the English language a power around the world is the power of those who speak it.

There was a time when it was said that the sun never sets on the British Empire. Reflecting on Great Britain's success in conquering land, especially in the Victorian era, Passetti (2016) highlights two factors: the use of weapons and the peaceful and diplomatic negotiation with other European powers. This last characteristic would have been known as *pax britannica*, a period of peace during the 19th century on the European continent, which allowed Great Britain time and resources in building its empire. Thus,

elevated to the position of great victorious, mistress of the seas, defender of European peace and free markets, Great Britain began to experience, at the beginning of the nineteenth century, the unique experience of becoming the main political power, as well as model and economic and social reference (PASSETTI, 2016, p.6).

The colonization process can be pointed out as one of the factors that historically contributed to the spread of the English language around the world. For instance, during the reign of Elizabeth I (1558 - 1603) there were at most 7 million native speakers of English. However, if we compare this number with the reign of Elizabeth II (1952 - present) we will observe that the number of native speakers of English increased approximately 50 times, reaching about 350 million native speakers³ (BAUER, 2002). In the following map, it is possible to observe the extension of the British Empire.

Figure 1: The extension of the British Empire

² Available at: <http://ipol.org.br/diagrama-mostra-as-linguas-mais-faladas-no-mundo/?fbclid=IwAR07LJ_MN6ONc-Q59HMijDAe-IWJLmpCMEa04xJVu8FWQtTc5Xsa-CcGEu-w>. Access in: 8 July 2021.

³ Data stated by Bauer (2002). According to the Word Tips website (2020), there are currently around 379,007,140 native English speakers.

Regarding the presence of the English language around the world, the linguist Kachru (CRYSTAL, 2003) proposes a model of language concentration divided into three circles. The first of them, internal, concerns the countries in which English is recognized as L1; in the second circle, external, we find the countries in which the presence of English was due to the colonization process by Great Britain; and in the third, expansion, we have the countries in which English is used as an additional language.

Figure 2: Kachru's model

Source: Crystal, 2003

Although the model developed by Kachru cannot encompass the most diverse scenarios in which we find the English language, Schneider (2011) emphasizes that the linguist succeeded in empowering English speakers and scholars in continents such as Africa and Asia. Furthermore, Schneider (2011) draws our attention to the nomenclature used by Kachru, where the words inner

word 'foreign'. That is, to weaken the view that English is a language that belongs to certain peoples and localities distant from Brazilian speakers.

and outer allude to the processes of sociopolitical inclusion and exclusion, as well as expanding indicates growth.

Thinking about the English language spoken in the three circles and not only in the inner circle, the expression World English(es) emerges. Bolton (2006) emphasizes that the term has been used in three different ways: the first one, as an umbrella term to indicate the most diverse varieties of English used around the world; the second one to refer to what is known as New Englishes, in which we have varieties of English that play the role of second language; the third one directly associated with the linguist Kachru where we find not only the description of different forms of English around the world, but also an attempt to value plurality and inclusion.

Due to its multifaceted character, the term World English(es) may present tensions, including a clash in the uses of the singular form World English and the plural form World Englishes. An advocate of the singular term, Rajagopalan (2005) emphasizes that his use of World English is not synonymous with political relativism, as put by Pennycook in his famous book *Critical Applied Linguistics: A Critical Introduction* (2001). Rajagopalan (2005) argues that there is no implication that all varieties of the English language have the same value when using the singular version of the term.

Whether through a macro vision, focused on the ways and conditions in which the English language is used worldwide nowadays, or through a micro perspective, in which there is a local cultural valorization, conceiving the existence of World English(es) means breaking the crystallized vision of the English language as an object belonging to the countries found in the inner circle proposed by Kachru (apud CRYSTAL, 2003). Such vision corroborates the attempt to obstruct the sense of inferiority and strangeness of speakers considered non-native English speakers.

However, we should still use Kachru's circles proposal (apud CRYSTAL, 2003) in a critical way. As aforementioned, Schneider (2011) alerts us to the nomenclature used by Kachru to define the circles, where the opposition of the terms inner and outer refers to power hierarchies. In other words, the countries in the inclusion circle are those with greater power, while those in the outer circle have less power. Furthermore, the use of the term expanding shows us the constant growth of English speakers as an additional language, showing us also an increase in the power of the countries in this circle.

Nevertheless, by grouping countries into categories, we may be led to have an interpretation that countries that are part of the same circle are on an equal footing with regard to holding power. Bourdieu (1983, p.165) warns us that "it follows from the expanded definition of competence that a language is worth what those who speak it are worth, i.e., the power and authority in the economic and cultural power relations of the holders of the corresponding competence". Thus, we are led to wonder: does the United States of America have the same reference weight for the teaching of English as New Zealand, for instance? Both countries are part of the inner circle but have different scopes in terms of influence on the processes of English language teaching.

We should also pay attention to the fact that the hierarchies of Kachru's proposal also take place within the countries participating in the circles, including those of greater power holding. For instance, Received Pronunciation, the British accent used by the English royal family and associated with a high social class, is still the most used variant for English language teaching when thinking of British English (SCHNEIDER, 2011), which means that we have more Received Pronunciation speakers in the outer circle than in the inner circle (CRYSTAL, 2002). This just shows us the hierarchy of variants of the English language that exist in the UK, for example. Thus, we have a threefold hierarchy: 1. a hierarchy of variants within the countries that are part of the circles; 2. a hierarchy among the variants of the countries of the same circle and 3. a hierarchy of variants among the countries of distinct circles.

Silva (2012) highlights that the digital revolution and the globalization of capitalism nowadays have been producing a change in the profile of individuals about the representations and epistemologies. Such change requires a new worldview, open to new conceptions and uses of language. Once we establish the English language as the voice of the 21st century processes of globalization and technological advance, it is not surprising to conceive the English language through new ideas and paradigms. It is along this path that the conception of World English(es) can alert us about the singular way the English language has been used in the last decades, drawing our attention to the articulations found between the English language, the speaker and the linguistic empire. Teaching, for example, through the perspective of World English(s) means avoiding any hint of erasure of the learner's culture, an aversion to the idea of cultural hierarchization, which can make those who find themselves in the role of owners of the English language uncomfortable.

3 The consequences of a lack of linguistic diversity in the English language classroom

The first reason for advocating the presence of linguistic diversity in the English language classroom concerns a tension in the linguistic imperialism existing in English language teaching. Linguistic plurality, through teaching materials, for instance, values the regionalities of English found in the countries of the inner, outer and expanding circles, as well as the learners' identities. Such valorization may start a trend in the production of teaching materials, causing a tension in the linguistic imperialism presented in English language teaching textbooks.

Moreover, linguistic diversity generates a crisis in the belief that we should speak English like natives. Due to a perspective of English associated with the view of the native speaker as being the owner of the language, some students may feel unmotivated in the language learning process (SILVEIRA, 2020), when only one standard variant is taken into consideration by the teacher. Since, within this conception, the English language belongs to other peoples, conceived as perfect by being spoken by them (COSTA LEITE, OLIVEIRA and COURA, 2020), the student may feel pressured not to commit acts that are considered mistakes, to cancel his accent and follow very specific models of pronunciation. In other words, when the textbook presents only one linguistic variant, the student may be led to think that everything that differs from the variant presented is incorrect. By following this thought, we have a greater probability of dissatisfaction of the student, who in many cases, will have the feeling that they will never reach the right one, synonymous here with identical reproduction of the models presented by the teacher or by the pedagogical support material.

4 Elaboration of didactic activity

We have decided to use the Common European Framework of Reference - CEFR as a guideline for the didactic activity because it is widely used in the Brazilian context of English language teaching and learning, working, even, as an indicative parameter of linguistic level in didactic materials. Besides, we will work with the European framework, since we do not have any other Brazilian option, which, in our understanding, could be more compatible with the purposes and perspectives of this research.

Result of a work started in 1991, the Common European Framework of Reference - CEFR is a categorization system of language proficiency (NUNES and CELIN, 2011). The use of this model is justified to the extent that it is employed in various contexts involving the use of additional languages, such as teaching and learning languages, preparation of teaching materials, proficiency exams, etc., which ended up propagating its popularity (CANI and SANTIAGO, 2018). In view of this, the CEFR can situate the teacher, giving a perspective about which student profile is more expected for the execution of the proposed activity.

The CEFR is structured around six different levels of proficiency in an additional language, as follows: Breakthrough, Waystage, Threshold, Vantage, Effective Operational Proficiency and Mastery (CONSELHO DA EUROPA, 2001). The levels can be arranged into three general groups, as shown below:

Figure 3: Division of CEFR levels

Source: European council, 2001.

The purpose of presenting a didactic activity in this paper is to show that English language teaching can go beyond an exclusively linguistic teaching. In other words, it is expected that the students, together with the teacher, reflect about the importance of linguistic diversity, breaking the hegemony of certain groups, peoples or communities over others, strengthening education as a political act. Since the content of the activities is of utmost importance, the exercises were made based on the content-based approach (LEFFA, 2016). In this approach, the material is not developed from linguistic topics, but from topics of the content itself (LEFFA, 2016). There is, then,

an expectation that the student learns not only the desired language itself, but also the content presented in conjunction with the language.

According to Mehisto et al. (2008), the Content and Language Integrated Learning (CLIL) approach has as its main objective the teaching of a target language in association with content, proposing links between the language to be learned and other school topics or even the ones that are of interest to the student. Moreover, through the association between language and content, there is the presence of greater interdisciplinarity, even promoting teamwork among teachers of different contents.

Another English language teaching approach that provides an association between language and content teaching is Content Based Instruction, CBI. Villalobos (2014) defines CBI as a language teaching approach in which the learner learns a language through content. Although the overall goal may be the same between CLIL and CBI, there are authors such as Brown and Bradford (2017) who differentiate the approaches, mainly pointing out a hierarchy between target language and content in the CBI approach, which does not happen in CLIL. In other words, according to these authors, the major goal in CBI classes is the learning of the target language, although students can also learn the content associated with it. However, in CLIL this hierarchy is not found and the content taught is as important as the target language.

The activity presented in this article was structured based on the topic, the objectives, the Common European Framework of Reference - CEFR, the context of application and the steps. Through this elaboration, it is intended to have a more organised activity, facilitating future use.

In addition, the topic "application context" was included to signal the conjuncture in which the activity was thought. At the time of the elaboration of the activity, part of Brazilian education took place remotely, as a consequence of the restriction of face-to-face interactions due to the propagation of COVID-19. Thus, we will find in this category an indication of a possible

application of the activity, which can be intended for face-to-face teaching, remote teaching, or both, with some adaptations.

Finally, we must emphasize that the proposed activities, when applied, can be adapted, since it is possible to find in each student or classroom his/her own characteristics and challenges.

5 Didactic activity

It will be presented below a didactic activity aimed at teaching and learning English. The activity was developed from a reflection about the importance of linguistic diversity in the English language classroom. Besides, it is worth mentioning that, in case of an application of the activity, adaptations by the teacher are welcomed.

5.1 Activity

This activity was intended as a way of highlighting the notion of the English language as the official language of several countries (as opposed to the more popular idea that divides the English language into British and American English).

Through this activity, we can expand the students' cultural capital related to the language they are learning, broadening the students' reflections and their global insertion.

Theme: Vocabulary used in New Zealand.

Objective: To introduce students to words commonly used in New Zealand English.

CEFR: A2 - B1.

Application context: Face-to-face teaching.

Steps: 1. The teacher shows the following flag and asks the class "Do you know this flag? Which country does this flag represent?"

Figure 4: New Zealand's flag

Source: Exame, 2014

In case the students do not know, the teacher can tell them that they are seeing the New Zealand flag. The teacher can even write the name of the country on the board.

2. The teacher puts the students into pairs. He then asks "What do you know about New Zealand? Share it with your partner". In case students do not know much information about the country, the teacher can put on the board some topics for students to discuss, such as: language (Which language is spoken in New Zealand?), territory size (Is new Zealand a big or a small country?), culture (Do you know any artist from New Zealand?), etc. It is important for the teacher to make it clear that students cannot consult the internet or other material during this activity (in the face-to-face format, consultation may decrease engagement in the game that will be proposed next; in the online format, it will be necessary to adapt this step, as students will most likely consult it).

3. The teacher explains that the students, still in pairs, will participate in a game. The game will be in the format of questions and answers, with alternatives. For this type of game, it is possible to use free digital platforms (such as Kahoot or Quizizz⁵, for example, where the teacher has the possibility to create his/her own games), which can bring dynamicity and motivation to the lesson,

⁵ To do so, access <<https://kahoot.com/>> and <<https://quizizz.com/?fromBrowserLoad=true>>, respectively.

in situations where students have access to technological devices. In the absence of access, if the teacher has resources such as a projector, he or she can use the projection for students to read the questions and options. As a last possibility, the teacher can hand out the questions of the activity on a printed sheet of paper. It is important that the teacher guides the activity, reading question by question.

1. What is the language spoken in New Zealand?

A. Spanish B. French C. English

2. In which continent is New Zealand located?

A. Asia B. Oceania C. Europe

3. What is the capital of New Zealand?

A. Wellington B. Hamilton C. Auckland

4. If you were born in New Zealand, you are...

A. Zealander B. New Zealander C. New Zealngian

5. Which country colonised New Zealand?

A. Spain B. United States C. Great Britain

4. The teacher gives the students a new activity. This time they should read the sentences of the exercise, paying attention to the words highlighted in bold (NAUMAI NZ, 2021)⁶ that are

⁶ NauMai NZ is the official website of the New Zealand government which contains information for international students who reside or will reside in the country. Website available at: <<https://naumainz.studyinnewzealand.govt.nz/>>. Access in: 08 June 2021

commonly used in New Zealand. They then have to put the bold words into the crossword puzzle according to the definitions given.

- A. John is always with me. He is a huge **bro!**
- B. Mary worked the entire day. She is really **buggered**.
- C. Arthur is on a diet. He has been eating **heaps** of vegetables and fruits.
- D. Mary went to the beach wearing her new **jandals**.
- E. Sonya is really **stoked** with her math grade. She had an A.
- F. Leo isn't Brazilian. He is a **Kiwi**.
- G. Cathy bought a beautiful **jumper** to wear in the winter time.
- H. Eduard was not hungry. He only ate **a bit** of his food.
- I. Emma bought new **togs**. She is going to the club tomorrow.

Figure 5: crossword puzzle

Down

1. Really tired
3. A lot, many
5. Swimsuit
8. A little

Across

2. Sweater
4. Supper happy
6. Friend
7. Flip flops
9. Person born in New Zealand (informal)

Source: Made by the authors through the website Educolorir⁷

5. The teacher writes on the board or hands out a printed version of the text below, highlighting the bold words in the text.

Mary is very **guttet** today. She didn't do her homework because she **had a mare** yesterday. Her mother prepared a delicious lunch and Mary ate too much. After a while, Mary started **to feel crook**.

The teacher can read the short text with the students. He then asks students to look at the highlighted expressions (NAUMAI NZ, 2021), commonly used in New Zealand, relating the columns in the following exercise.

- | | | |
|----|-----------------------|--------------------------------------|
| A. | <i>Feeling gutted</i> | () <i>Feeling ill</i> |
| B. | <i>Having a mare</i> | () <i>Feeling upset</i> |
| C. | <i>Feeling crook</i> | () <i>Having a hard or bad time</i> |

After correcting the activity above, the teacher asks students to answer the following questions:

- A. *Why is Mary feeling gutted today?*
- B. *What did Mary's mother prepare?*
- C. *Why did Mary feel crook?*

⁷ Website available at: <<https://www.educolorir.com/crosswordgenerator.php>>. Access in: 08 June 2021.

6. As a homework assignment, the teacher asks students to research a famous New Zealander by answering the questions below. The answers can be organised in the order of the questions presented below creating a short text.

A. What is the name of this Kiwi?

B. In which city was this Kiwi born?

C. How old is this Kiwi?

D. What does this Kiwi do?

The teacher can show the following text as a model:

Jacinda Ardern was born in **Hamilton**. She is **40 years old**. She is the **prime minister** of New Zealand.

7. Next class, the teacher can distribute the texts made by students to be read by classmates and ask them to compare what they found. As a way of thinking about interculturality, the teacher may suggest that the students establish parallels between famous Brazilian people and the famous New Zealanders they researched. Thus, it will be possible to make a comparison between Brazilian and New Zealand music styles (in case some student selects a singer), about political roles (which is the case of the text example mentioned above), among other issues that may emerge from the research brought by the students.

Table of answers

Step 3: 1.C, 2.B, 3.A, 4.B, 5.C

Step 4:

Figure 6: Table of answers of the crossword puzzle about words used in New Zealand

Source: Made by the authors through the website Educolorir

Step 5:

- A. *Feeling gutted* (C) *Feeling ill.*
- B. *Having a mare* (A) *Feeling upset.*
- C. *Feeling Crook* (B) *Having a hard or bad time.*

A. *Why is Mary feeling gutted today?*

Because she didn't do her homework.

B. *What did Mary's mother prepare?*

Mary's mother prepared lunch.

C. *Why did Mary feel crook?*

Because she ate too much lunch.

Final considerations

In English language classes, it is possible for us to think of some situations in which English is associated with power. As discussed, the relation between British English and American English shows us the crystallized articulation of English with both countries mentioned. Such alliance is built through the belief of the native speaker, holder of legitimate linguistic knowledge, and also through the domination processes exercised by Great Britain and the United States of America, such as colonization and the current economic-cultural influence, respectively. The presentation of the didactic activity of this paper should be seen, therefore, as an attempt of reflection, showing the students that the English language should not be conceived as belonging to certain people, limiting the learning process and legitimating exclusively certain cultures.

So, how should the English language teacher proceed? The first step that can be taken is to reflect on the processes of power, noticing the discourses that naturalize what is not natural, observing how the teaching and learning of the English language go beyond merely communicative factors. Secondly, the teacher can ponder on the reflections that this linguistic imperialism has on English learners. From then on, there is the possibility for the teacher to conduct his/her work in a more critical way, finding spaces, whenever possible, for the introduction of linguistic diversity in his/her classes.

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